

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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ACUTE BILIARY PANCREATITIS: AGE AND GENDER DIFFERENCES IN CLINICAL PRESENTATION**Alidjanov F.B.¹, Khomidov M.A.², Abdulakhatov M.Kh.², Elmuradov G.K.², Radzhabov A.I.³**¹Center for the Development of Professional Qualifications of Medical Workers, Tashkent, Uzbekistan²Republican Scientific Center of Emergency Medical Care, Tashkent, Uzbekistan³Central Hospital of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Resume. *Objective.* To assess the frequency of biliary etiology among patients with acute pancreatitis and to analyze the age- and sex-related characteristics of acute biliary pancreatitis. *Materials and Methods.* A retrospective analysis was performed of the medical records of 302 patients admitted to the surgical departments of the Republican Scientific Center of Emergency Medical Care in 2022-2025 with a preliminary diagnosis of acute pancreatitis. Patients transferred from other hospitals, including those after recently performed endoscopic papillosphincterotomy, were excluded from the study. The diagnosis was established according to the Revised Atlanta Classification and the 2012 international consensus. *Results.* The diagnosis of acute pancreatitis was confirmed in 255 of 302 patients (84.4%). Biliary etiology was identified in 225 of 255 confirmed cases (88.2%). Among patients with acute biliary pancreatitis, women accounted for 71.1% and men for 28.9%. No statistically significant difference in mean age was found between women and men (52.0 ± 18.2 vs. 52.9 ± 16.4 years; $p=0.642$). The female-to-male ratio varied across age groups, reaching its highest value in middle age and decreasing in older patients. *Conclusion.* Acute biliary pancreatitis was the predominant form of acute pancreatitis in the studied cohort. The limited sensitivity of transabdominal ultrasonography and the low sensitivity of ALT elevation support the need for a comprehensive diagnostic approach using additional imaging modalities.

Keywords: acute biliary pancreatitis, gallstone disease, cholelithiasis, age, sex, diagnosis, ultrasonography, alanine aminotransferase.

ЎТКИР БИЛИАР ПАНКРЕАТИТ: КЛИНИК НАМОЁН БЎЛИШИДА ЁШ ВА ЖИНСГА ОИД ФАРҚЛАР**Алижанов Ф.Б.¹, Хомидов М.А.², Абдулахатов М.Х.², Элмуратов Г.К.², Раджабов А.И.³**¹Тиббиёт ходимларининг касбий малакасини ривожлантириш маркази, Тошкент ш., Ўзбекистон²Республика шошилинич тиббий ёрдам илмий маркази, Тошкент ш., Ўзбекистон³Ўзбекистон Республикаси Ички Ишлар Вазирлиги Марказий клиник шифохонаси, Тошкент ш., Ўзбекистон

Резюме. *Мақсад.* Ўткир панкреатит билан касалланган беморлар орасида билиар этиологиянинг учраш частотасини баҳолаш ҳамда ўткир билиар панкреатитнинг ёш ва жинсга боғлиқ хусусиятларини таҳлил қилиш. *Материаллар ва усуллар.* Республика Шошилинич Тиббий Ёрдам Илмий Марказининг жарроҳлик бўлимларига 2022–2025 йилларда ўткир панкреатит дастлабки таиҳиси билан ётқизилган 302 нафар беморнинг тиббий ҳужжатлари ретроспектив таҳлил қилинди. Бошқа шифохоналардан ўтказилган беморлар, жумладан яқинда эндоскопик папилосфинктеротомия ўтказилган беморлар тадқиқотдан чиқариб ташланди. Таиҳис қайта кўриб чиқилган Атланта таснифи ва 2012 йилги халқаро консенсусга мувофиқ қўйилди. *Натижалар.* 302 нафар бемордан 255 нафариди (84,4%) ўткир панкреатит таиҳиси тасдиқланди. Тасдиқланган 255 та ҳолатдан 225 тасида (88,2%) билиар этиология аниқланди. Ўткир билиар панкреатит билан касалланган беморлар орасида аёллар 71,1% ни, эркаклар эса 28,9% ни ташиқил этди. Аёллар ва эркаклар ўртача ёши орасида статистик жиҳатдан аҳамиятли фарқ аниқланмади ($52,0 \pm 18,2$ ва $52,9 \pm 16,4$ ёш; $p=0,642$). Аёл ва эркаклар нисбати ёш гуруҳлари бўйича турлича бўлиб, энг юқори кўрсаткичга ўрта ёшда эришилди ва кекса ёшли беморларда пасайди. Хулоса. Тадқиқ этилган когортада ўткир билиар панкреатит — ўткир панкреатитнинг асосий шакли бўлди. Трансабдоминал ультратовуш текширувининг чекланган сезгирлиги ва ALT кўтарилишининг паст сезгирлиги қўшимча визуализация усулларида фойдаланган ҳолда комплекс диагностик ёндашувга бўлган эҳтиёжни тасдиқлайди.

Калит сўзлар: ўткир билиар панкреатит, ўт-тош касаллиги, холецистолитиаз, ёш, жинс, диагностика, ультратовуш текшируви, аланинаминотрансфераза.

ОСТРЫЙ БИЛИАРНЫЙ ПАНКРЕАТИТ: ВОЗРАСТНЫЕ И ГЕНДЕРНЫЕ РАЗЛИЧИЯ В КЛИНИЧЕСКИХ ПРОЯВЛЕНИЯХ

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Резюме. Цель. Оценить частоту билиарной этиологии среди пациентов с острым панкреатитом и проанализировать возрастные и гендерные особенности острого билиарного панкреатита. Материалы и методы. Проведён ретроспективный анализ медицинской документации 302 пациентов, поступивших в хирургические отделения Республиканского научного центра экстренной медицинской помощи в 2022–2025 годах с предварительным диагнозом «острый панкреатит». Из исследования были исключены пациенты, переведённые из других стационаров, в том числе после недавно выполненной эндоскопической папиллосфинктеротомии. Диагноз устанавливался в соответствии с пересмотренной Атлантской классификацией и международным консенсусом 2012 года. Результаты. Диагноз острого панкреатита был подтверждён у 255 из 302 пациентов (84,4%). Билиарная этиология установлена у 225 из 255 подтверждённых случаев (88,2%). Среди пациентов с острым билиарным панкреатитом женщины составили 71,1%, мужчины — 28,9%. Статистически значимых различий по среднему возрасту между женщинами и мужчинами не выявлено ($52,0 \pm 18,2$ против $52,9 \pm 16,4$ года; $p=0,642$). Соотношение женщин и мужчин варьировало в зависимости от возрастной группы, достигая максимальных значений в среднем возрасте и снижаясь у пациентов старших возрастных групп. Заключение. Острый билиарный панкреатит являлся преобладающей формой острого панкреатита в исследуемой когорте. Ограниченная чувствительность трансабдоминальной ультрасонографии и низкая чувствительность повышения АЛТ обосновывают необходимость комплексного диагностического подхода с использованием дополнительных методов визуализации.

Ключевые слова: острый билиарный панкреатит, желчнокаменная болезнь, холелитиаз, возраст, пол, диагностика, ультрасонография, аланинаминотрансфераза.

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Introduction. The overall incidence of acute pancreatitis varies widely between countries, ranging from 13 to 45 cases per 100,000 population per year, while the incidence of the biliary form is reported to be approximately 5-25 cases per 100,000 population [1, 2].

Among the etiological factors of acute pancreatitis, biliary pathology plays a leading role. Acute biliary pancreatitis is the most common form of acute pancreatitis and develops as a result of migration of gallstones or biliary sludge into the distal common bile duct, followed by transient or persistent obstruction of the major duodenal papilla. The clinical significance of acute biliary pancreatitis is determined by the high recurrence rate, the risk of local and systemic complications, and the need for timely intervention on the biliary tract [1-3].

It is known that the prevalence of gallstone disease, and consequently acute biliary pancreatitis, depends substantially on sex, age, ethnic and regional characteristics, as well as demographic factors [1-5]. Therefore, the study of age- and sex-related characteristics of acute biliary pancreatitis in specific populations has important scientific and practical value.

Objective. The objective of the study was to assess the frequency of biliary etiology among patients with acute pancreatitis and to analyze the age- and sex-related characteristics of acute biliary pancreatitis.

Materials and Methods. A retrospective analysis was performed of the medical records of 302 patients admitted to the surgical departments of the Republican Scientific Center of Emergency Medical Care in 2022-2025 with a preliminary diagnosis of acute pancreatitis. Patients transferred from other hospitals, including those after recently performed endoscopic papillosphincterotomy, were excluded from the study.

The diagnosis of acute pancreatitis was established in accordance with the Revised Atlanta Classification and the 2012 international consensus. Diagnostic criteria included a typical clinical picture, laboratory abnormalities such as serum and urinary amylase activity and alanine aminotransferase (ALT) level, as well as findings of instrumental examination. Biliary etiology of acute pancreatitis was determined by the presence of signs of gallstone disease, including gallstones or biliary sludge in the gallbladder and/or bile ducts, according to imaging methods. All patients underwent transabdominal ultrasonography; multislice computed tomography or magnetic resonance imaging was performed when clinically indicated.

Considering that the detection of gallstones, especially microliths and sludge, in the gallbladder by transabdominal ultrasonography in patients with acute pancreatitis is not ideal and may be below 80%, the diagnostic value of ALT level for differentiating biliary pancreatitis from other etiological forms was also analyzed [5-10].

Results. Among 302 patients, the diagnosis of acute pancreatitis was confirmed in 255 cases (84.4%). In the remaining patients, further examination revealed other acute abdominal diseases, including perforation or exacerbation of peptic ulcer disease, acute cholecystitis, erosive gastritis, and mesenteric vascular thrombosis. Among patients with confirmed acute pancreatitis, serum amylase was elevated more than twofold in 167 of 240 examined patients (69.6%), and urinary amylase was elevated in 120 of 172 examined patients (69.8%). Ultrasonographic signs of acute pancreatitis were detected in 222 patients (87.1%). Multislice computed tomography or magnetic resonance imaging confirmed acute pancreatitis in 92 of 95 patients (96.8%). ALT elevation above 150 U/L was detected in 95 patients (42.2%). Biliary etiology was established in 225 of 255 patients with confirmed acute pancreatitis, accounting for 88.2% of cases (Table 1). These data indicate the predominance of the biliary form of acute pancreatitis in the studied region.

Table 1.

Etiological and sex distribution of acute pancreatitis

Type of pancreatitis	Women, n=170	Men, n=85	Total, n=255
Biliary	160 (94.1)	65 (76.4)	225 (88.2)
Non-biliary	10 (5.9)	20 (23.6)	30 (11.8)
Total	170 (100)	85 (100)	255 (100)

Among patients with acute biliary pancreatitis (n=225), women accounted for 71.1% (160/225) and men for 28.9% (65/225). The mean age of women (52.0±18.2 years) and men (52.9±16.4 years) did not differ significantly (p=0.642) (Table 2).

Analysis of different age groups revealed marked variation in the female-to-male ratio. In young patients, this ratio was 2.7; in middle-aged patients it increased to 3.2, followed by a decrease to 1.8 in the 60-74-year age group and a slight increase to 2.3 in elderly patients. This pattern may reflect the influence of hormonal and demographic factors (Figure 1).

Table 2.

Demographic characteristics of patients with acute biliary pancreatitis

Age, years	Women	Men	Total, n=225	Female/male ratio
18-44	60 (37.5)	22 (34.6)	82 (36.7)	2.7
45-59	47 (29.7)	15 (23.1)	62 (27.8)	3.2
60-74	35 (21.9)	20 (30.8)	55 (24.4)	1.8
75-90	18 (10.9)	8 (11.5)	26 (11.1)	2.3
Total	160	65	225	2.5
Mean age, M±SD	52.0±18.2	52.9±16.4	51.9±17.8	p=0.642

Note. Distribution by age groups: df=3; chi-square statistic=0.937; critical chi-square=7.815; p=0.817.

Fig. 1. Acute biliary pancreatitis by sex and age groups

Discussion. The pronounced predominance of acute biliary pancreatitis among other forms of acute pancreatitis in the studied cohort is probably associated with lifestyle and regional characteristics of the population, including a relatively low contribution of alcohol-related pancreatitis. An ALT level above 150 U/L showed high specificity (83.3%) for differentiating biliary pancreatitis from other etiological forms, but its sensitivity was limited (41.1%), and the overall diagnostic accuracy was 63.3%. Therefore, ALT elevation may be useful as an additional diagnostic marker, but it cannot replace imaging-based verification of biliary etiology. Among patients with acute biliary pancreatitis, women predominated, accounting for 71.1% of cases, whereas men accounted for 28.9%. The mean age did not differ significantly between sexes. However, the female-to-male ratio varied substantially across age groups and tended to decrease in older age groups. The high proportion of women with acute biliary pancreatitis may be related to the higher prevalence of gallstone disease, which is influenced by pregnancy, childbirth, hormonal factors, and demographic characteristics [11, 12]. At the early hospital stage, diagnostic errors occurred in a considerable proportion of patients with suspected acute pancreatitis. This supports the need for wider implementation of comprehensive diagnostic algorithms, including laboratory markers, transabdominal ultrasonography, and additional imaging modalities such as multislice computed tomography and magnetic resonance imaging when indicated.

Acute biliary pancreatitis was the dominant form of acute pancreatitis in the studied region and accounted for 88.2% of confirmed cases. The identified age- and sex-related features indicate a predominance of women with a tendency toward gradual equalization of the female-to-male ratio in older age groups. The limited sensitivity of transabdominal ultrasonography requires wider use of additional imaging methods in patients with suspected biliary pancreatitis.

Conclusion. Acute biliary pancreatitis was the predominant etiological form of acute pancreatitis in the studied cohort, accounting for 88.2% of confirmed cases. Women prevailed among patients with acute biliary pancreatitis, while the female-to-male ratio varied according to age group and tended to decrease in older patients. ALT elevation above 150 U/L demonstrated high specificity but low sensitivity for biliary etiology; therefore, it should be used as an additional criterion rather than as an independent diagnostic marker. The limited sensitivity of transabdominal ultrasonography in detecting microlithiasis and biliary sludge supports the need for a comprehensive diagnostic approach using additional imaging modalities in patients with suspected acute biliary pancreatitis.

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